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Prevalence Of Cervicogenic Headache Inpatients Suffering From Depression

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ABSTRACT

Background: Cervicogenic headache is very common among different age groups and gender, but now-a-days it is very common in age between 20-60 years. When a patient gets depressed, he presents with different symptoms, but the patients usually get cervicogenic headache because of persistent depression.

Aims & Objective: The purpose of this study was to evaluate the ratio of cervicogenic headache in patients suffered from depression regularly 10 to 12 or more days per month in specific settings.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted on the sample of 59, was selected from Madinah Teaching Hospital, Allied Hospital Faisalabad, DHQ hospital Faisalabad and psychiatry and mental care Faisalabad. Data was collected through purposive sampling technique. Those patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria was the part of that prevalence study. A headache impact test (HIT) questionnaire was confirm the cervicogenic headache in patients with depression.

INTRODUCTION:

Cervicogenic headache identifies as unilateral pain that originate from neck and radiate from articular and extra-articular structures. It is recurrent and chronic headache that usually aggravate by neck movements. CGH lead to decreased neck mobility.^[1] Cervicogenic headache can be aggravated by abnormal posture of head, movements of neck and load on tender points. Cervicogenic headache usually confused with other types of headaches i.e., tension-type headache or migraine.^[2]

Pathophysiology of CGH has not been accurately demonstrated. Hence, there is sufficient evidence that basic mechanism must be intersect. When afferents from 2 separate regions converge on the one 2nd-order neuron, activity of nociceptors along anyone of the afferents which can be presents as ache originating in term of others afferent.^[3]

CGH usually caused by trauma, persistent spasm of shoulder and neck muscles, strain, depression, and whiplash. Cervicogenic headache often related to stress, it may also result from cervical osteoarthritis, whiplash injury or damaged disc.^[4] Falling, taking stress, coldness or playing sports can trigger headache. Followings are some red flag symptoms for cervicogenic headache:

If intensity of headache becoming worse with time.

Sudden and persistent onset of headache

If patient suffered from high fever, stiff neck, or rash along with headache

Dizziness and vision changes along with headache

CGH is commonly occurring situation that affects most of the persons at a point in their lives. Pathology behind symptoms of headache are diverse, many and hard to differentiate. Headache's classification is based on assessment of symptoms of headache along with clinical testing.^[5]

Criteria for diagnosis for headache purposed 2-3 years ago. For neck pain and headache, there are many differential diagnoses. In addition, cervical musculoskeletal disorders involve myofascial Trps and forward head abnormal posture play role in most of the conditions. Diagnostic criteria for cervicogenic headache involve neck stiffness and pain along with headache.^[6]

Diagnostic criteria for CGH include same side head pain, symptoms of neck, non-clustering moderate ache starting in neck then radiate to head, response to nerve blockade or root, and some non-obligatory characteristics include dizziness, visual blurring, autonomic disturbance, sphonophotophobia and the painful swallowing.^[7]

Major symptoms of CGH are one-sided headache and symptoms radiating to neck. Pain characteristics include non-clustering ache, pain on episodes with increasing duration, moderate, non-excruciating ache and pain of throbbing nature.^[8] Other characteristics include blockage of occipital nerve or root C2 on affected side end the ache transiently, gives complete analgesia obtained. Female sex and neck/head trauma by history also included.

Rarely occurring, minor and non-obligatory symptoms include vomiting, ipsilateral edema, nausea, dizziness, less frequently-flushing, photo and phono- phobia, blurred vision on ipsilateral eye and swallowing difficulties.^[9]

Cervicogenic headache can be treated by medications, exercise and physical therapy. Nerve block can also be the treatment of cervicogenic headache, it helps in pain relief and work better with physiotherapy.^[10] Cervical mobilization and manipulation, strengthening of 2 cervico-scapular muscles, thoracic manipulation and self-applied cervical mobilization proved effective in reducing disability and pain and also helps to improve function.^[11]

In recent studies, cervicogenic headache diagnosed through international classification of headache society. ICH society make a distinct difference between tension-type, cervicogenic headache and migraine. Physiotherapy is the first line treatment/management. Therapeutic exercise and manipulative therapy seem to be effective in managing CGH. These maneuvers restoring nervous inhibitory system at specific levels on spine and stimulate inhibitory pathways.^[12]

Material and methods

A cross-sectional study design was conducted. All patient was selected from following settings: Madinah Teaching Hospital, Allied Hospital Faisalabad, DHQ hospital Faisalabad and Psychiatry and Mental Care Faisalabad. Approximately, it had taken 4 months duration to collect and analyze data after the approval of synopsis. Study population was depressed patients and based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. Sample size was 59. To collect sample purposive sampling technique was used.

Inclusion Criteria:

Patients between the age of 20-60 years.

Both (male and female) will be the part of our study.

Those patients will be selected who fulfill the criteria of international headache-society.

Exclusion Criteria:

Patients who are older than 60 year or younger than 20.

Those patients having cervicogenic headache after head surgery

Those patients having cervicogenic headache after cervical injury.

Data collection tools:

International headache society classification: According to the research of JASuijlekom et al, that criteria is of good reliability.

Headache impact test (HIT-6): HIT is reliable and valid instrument to assess frequency or intensity of headache.

Data Collection Procedure:

A cross-sectional study was conducted on the sample of 59, was selected from different hospital settings in Faisalabad. Data was collected through purposive sampling technique. Those patients who, fulfilling the inclusion criteria was the part of the prevalence study

Results

In this study 63 patients recruited and performed HIT-6 test on them who had already diagnosed with depression after informed consent. The male to female ratio was 32:68. The age range for the research we conducted was 20-60 years, our findings indicate that the mean age for cervicogenic headache was 36 years.

Figure 1: Bar chart of patient age

Figure 2: Pie chart for gender of patients

TABLE 1: THIT

THIT					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	little/no impact 49 or less	36	61.0	61.0	61.0
	some impact 50-55	8	13.6	13.6	74.6
	substantial impact 56-59	4	6.8	6.8	81.4
	severe impact 60-78	11	18.6	18.6	100.0
	Total	59	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 shows the interpretation of headache impact test, according to this table total values of HIT was categorized into 4 groups. 61.0 % were included in little/no impact 49 or less group, 13.6% were included in some impact 50-55 group, 6.8% were included in substantial impact 56-59 group and 18.6 % were included in severe impact 60-78 group. The mean of total HIT was 1.83 ± 1.91 .

Figure 3: THIT

Discussion:

This study showed relatively high prevalence of CGH in depressed patients. Many other studies on this topic have revealed varying degree of CGH in depressed patients ranges from 6.8% to 18.6%. It has been noted that when a person taken antidepressants, along with depression, headache also seems to improve because they are made to change neurotransmitter level.

59 patients had been taken in recent study having age ranges between 20-60 years. 52.5 percent were under the category of 20-30 years, 23.7% were under the category of 31-40 years, 18.6% were under the category of 41-50 years and 5.1% were under the category of 51-60 years. We had taken 19 male patients and 40 female patients.

Knackstedt H et al. studied show that the prevalence of CGH in people aged 30-44 in a general population. It discovered that the cervical range of motion was significantly decreased when compared to healthy controls and that the pericranial muscle tenderness score was significantly greater on the side with pain than the side without pain. While some epidemiological research recruited people of older ages, selecting a relatively young study population carries a risk of underestimating the prevalence. The low prevalence of CEH in our study is not likely due to the telephone interview because only 23% of the participants were questioned over the phone and 77% of the participants were interviewed in-person. The classification that is used has a significant impact on prevalence. Based on the unilateral origin of the pain, we distinguished between CGH and chronic headache due to whiplash injury. In theory, CEH is described as a unilateral headache without side shift.^[13]

Sjaastad O et al. reported a frequency of 4.1%. There was a male preponderance in the 41 instances with the highest number of CEH criteria ('core' cases). While cervicogenic qualities were common in CGH, 'migraine traits' such as nausea, vomiting, and throbbing appeared to be uncommon. Exacerbations of pain commenced in the neck/occipital area in 97% of the patients.^[14]

Rao K et al reported. When compared to patients with other complaints in the control group, patients with a primary complaint of CGH had a significantly high prevalence of depressive symptoms. Other research

on this topic has reported variable degrees of depression among headache sufferers ranging from 3.4% to 78%. Because both sadness and headache are frequent disorders, we cannot say if they are connected or just coexist. This theory, however, is flawed since CGH is not as frequent as other types of headache, such as migraine. Furthermore, there is evidence that depression may contribute to the level of pain associated with headaches. Both pain and sadness have been shown to impair function.^[15]

Gupta ravi et al. studied find headache individuals acquired mild depression over time, but the headache was only found in moderate to severe depression patients, and it was more likely in them to progress. These findings suggest that headache does not cause depression in and of itself, but rather depression causes headache when it reaches a threshold level. To the best of our knowledge, no data is available in this area, and more research is needed. Another significant result was the lack of relationship between any specific category of headache and depression. Despair does not seem to increase headache, and headache increasing should alert one to look for causes other than accompanying despair. Depression is similarly related with several subtypes of headaches, implying that these subtypes may share or overlap in pathogenesis. (39) Cervicogenic headache (CGH), as the name implies, is a headache of cervical origin. Historically, these headaches were difficult to identify and treat due to a lack of understanding of their etiology and pathophysiology. Even today, managing a CGH is difficult for sports rehabilitation professionals. The goal of this clinical recommendation is to do a literature evaluation on CGH and design an evidence-based method to CGH assessment and clinical therapy. The particular etiology of CGHs is yet unknown, but it is believed that upper cervical neck dysfunction is the source of the condition. Cervicogenic headaches are linked to musculoskeletal dysfunction, muscle imbalance, and recognizable patterns of tension and weakening in the muscles. An appropriate diagnosis will result from a complete history and clinical examination. A multi-modal physical therapy solution, combining modalities, manual therapy, and therapeutic exercise, is advised to address specific deficits, as it is with other musculoskeletal dysfunctions. To get the athlete with CGHs back to sports as quickly as feasible, sports physical therapists must establish an accurate diagnosis and offer a suitable intervention.^[10]

Louter MA et al. studied show that Depression over the course of one's life is roughly three times more likely in people who use CGH. Patients with active disease have a significant prevalence of present depression, which is partly brought on by current nocturnal attacks' impact on sleep.

Song T-J et al. reported that Previous clinic-based investigations on participants with headache who also had anxiety and depression revealed that a sizable fraction of participants with headache also had anxiety and depression. 53.4% and 36.9% of participants in an Italian study were said to have anxiety and depression, respectively. The prevalence of anxiety and depression was found to be 17% and 21%, respectively, in patients with chronic headaches, according to a different clinic-based study conducted in America. However, there have been few reports of anxiety and sadness in headache individuals using population-level data. In this population-based investigation, we discovered that a modest but statistically significant number of people with headache experienced anxiety or depression.^[11]

Martelletti P et al. studied show that Cervicogenic headache, which develops from structures in the neck, is a rather common but yet debatable type of headache. The range of the disorder's estimated prevalence, from 0.7% to 13.8%, is rather wide.^[13]

Thukar M et al. studied that Inferential statistics are the foundation of this work. IHS criteria were applied in this investigation to diagnose CEH in patients. In the 2007 research by Tony Hall, et al., he claimed that CEH has I.H.S. categorised it. In a further research by C. Wober-Bingol et al.10 in 1994 with 437 patients using IHS criteria, he discovered that IHS criteria were helpful in identifying headache in patients of the child and adolescent age range, with definitive diagnoses being made in almost 70% of cases.^[14]

The incidence of CEH in the group of people who have frequent headaches is 15.6%, demonstrating that CEH is a more prevalent kind of headache than migraine and tension-type headaches (TTH). In 1995, Niels Nilsson11 came to the conclusion from his research that CEH is a more prevalent type of headache than

migraine and TTH. Another intriguing research by Tony Hall, Ho Tak Chan, Kim Robinson, et al.² indicated that CEH is a kind of headache recognised by the I.H.S. and makes up between 15% and 20% of all chronic and recurring headaches.^[15]

CONCLUSION

Present study concluded that HIT-6 can be used to assess patients with cervicogenic headache which is one of the types of headache. After receiving informed consent, we included 59 patients in our research and conducted HIT-6 test on patients who was already diagnosed with depression. The findings of HIT-6, which we performed on 59 patients, revealed that the prevalence of cervicogenic headache is 39% in depressed patients.

Limitation:

Study is restricted by certain factors. Firstly, in the recent study sample size was small only 59 participants were added, which can destroy the validity and generalizability of results. Secondary, due to short duration and limited number of settings quality of research compromised.

Strength of study:

The strength of our study is that prevalence of CGH have been seen in depressed patients. Frequency/intensity of CGH assessed through HIT, which is of high variability and validity. Data collection and procedure has been done properly and accurately.

Recommendations:

Based on our findings, we recommend that following recommendations should be approved by other researcher to further improve the quality of research.

Further study should be done on large sample size.

Time duration of study should be increased for better results.

Number of settings should be increased.

Conflict of Interest: None

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Authors Contributions:

KF, MA, J and IT contributed to conception and design. KF, MA, J contributed to data acquisition. KF, MA, J, IT and RZ contributed to data analysis. IT contributed to article drafting and revising it critically for important intellectual content. All authors approved the version of manuscript to be published

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